

Definition of circular economy indicators for Living Labs

Deliverable 4.2

D4.2 Definition of circular economy indicators for Living Labs

Review of existing circular economy indicators and list of indicators adapted to a water-smart society in the B-WaterSmart context.

Summary

Objectives

The main objective of Deliverable 4.2 is to define a **set of indicators** to measure circular economy (CE) around the **water-energy-resources-waste** nexus in the B-WaterSmart project context. This set of indicators will contribute to the B-WaterSmart assessment framework that will allow to monitor and evaluate each Living Lab (LL) (industry(ies), municipality, city, region, etc.) performance according to the defined circular opportunities.

Methodology

The WP4 team from B-WaterSmart has analysed different sources in order to evaluate the state of the art for measuring CE through indicators, analysing which indicators and criteria have been published until now and gathering and adapting all the CE related indicators that could be applicable in the context of B-WaterSmart. After this review, an extended first set of indicators was proposed and then was shared and discussed in a workshop with the WP4 team, the LLs and other interested members from the project. The aim of this workshop was to finally determine which indicators could be monitored in each LL and could be of interest in the context of CE and the B-WaterSmart project. After the workshop, a prioritization and simplification of the indicators proposed initially was made. Later, the CE indicators were discussed with Work Package 6 (WP6) – who will develop a water-smartness framework – to integrate them with those from WP6, aligned with the definition of water smartness and their strategic objectives and assessment criteria. A second round showing the indicators to all interested members was done, to get the approval from the WP4 team and to get a final list of CE indicators to be monitored later in each LL.

Results and findings

The final results of the present Deliverable 4.2. are:

- a list of different sources and scientific articles reviewed and updated until today about CE related indicators;
- a set of 28 CE indicators related to the water sector and the water-energy-resources-waste nexus, which have been validated with all the WP4 team members;
- a set of indicators that will contribute to the B-WaterSmart assessment framework and is expected to be replicated beyond the scope of this project.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AA	Aquatic Acidification
AWARE	Available Water Remaining
CE	Circular Economy
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
CFP	Carbon Footprint
CGRi	Circularity Gap Reporting Initiative
COTEC	Council of occupational therapists for the European countries
E	Ecotoxicity
EASAC	The European Academies' Science Advisory Council
EEA	European Environment Agency
ENEL	Ente Nazionale per l'Energia ELettrica
EoL	End-of-Life
Eu	Eutrophication
EURES	EU Resources Efficiency Scoreboard
Eurostat	European Statistical Office
GCM	Global Circularity Metric
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GWP	Global Warning Potential
INE	Instituto Nacional de Estadística
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IWA	International Water Association
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCT	Life Cycle Thinking
LL	Living Lab
MFA	Material Flow Analysis
N	Nitrogen
NaCl	Sodium chloride
NCM	National Circularity Metric
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
P	Phosphorus
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PPP	Purchasing Power Parity
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
WBCSD	World Business Council for Sustainable Development
WP	Work Package
WS	Water Scarcity
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant

Executive summary

The main objective of the B-WaterSmart project is to accelerate the transformation towards **water-smart economies and societies** in coastal Europe and beyond. This will be achieved by co-creating innovative solutions to face sustainability challenges and secure water access and quality for the generations to come. With this objective it has been selected six coastal cities and regions – named Living Labs (LLs) – with the ambition to tackle the challenges and opportunities of implementing water-smart technologies. In this context, the Work Package 4 (WP4) aims to promote resource recovery, circular economy, and ecosystem regeneration in the different LLs located in Alicante, Bodø, East Frisia, Flanders, Lisbon and Venice.

Previously, Task 4.1 identified the current context of CE initiatives in the LLs by describing a map and the main stakeholders involved in each one. This Task contributed to the previous Deliverable (D4.1), where data specifications and type of information required from the LLs to evaluate circularity were also provided.

The present deliverable (**D4.2**) is part of **Task 4.2** and intends to guide the reader through the state of the art of existing circular economy (CE) related indicators and to present a list of CE indicators adapted to a water-smart society, in the B-WaterSmart context, embracing the water-energy-resources-waste nexus. From the data and information required in the D4.1 and then provided by the LLs, these indicators will be calculated and will allow to monitor and evaluate the performance of each Living Lab (LL), region, city, etc. according to the defined circular opportunities during the development of Task 4.2 until the end of the project (and possibly beyond). Those circular opportunities will also be connected and coordinated with the CoPs architecture and stakeholder mapping for each LL from WP1 (Deliverable 1.1).

At the same time, Task 4.3 is going on, identifying existing and new circular business models along the different existing nexus between water, energy, resources and waste in each LL.

This Deliverable 4.2 is structured in 4 main chapters related to CE indicators.

- **Chapter 1** presents an introduction about the importance of measuring circularity in products, processes, companies, etc. and how they can enhance reaching sustainability. It also explains why is important to identify CE indicators and how to measure them.
- **Chapter 2** is a state of the art of existing sources providing CE related indicators and how they are classified. It also focuses on CE indicators approaching the water-energy-resources-waste nexus which are aligned within the B-WaterSmart context.
- In **Chapter 3** the methodology for choosing the indicators and a list of **28 CE indicators** for the B-WaterSmart project is presented. Additionally, there is a brief introduction into new emergent guidelines and standards related to CE and it is proposed how they will contribute to the circularity evaluation of the LLs, regions, cities, etc. in the context of B-WaterSmart.
- Finally, **Chapter 4** describes the main conclusions from the present D4.2.

The results from D4.2 and from the future ones are expected to be applied beyond the duration and scope of this project to other areas, regions, cities, etc.

1 Introduction

1.1 The importance of measuring circularity

Circular Economy (CE) is an approach to encourage the cyclical and responsible use of resources. It is a way to transform the current system and it is based, according to Ellen MacArthur Foundation (E. M., 2021), on three principles: eliminate waste and pollution, keep products and materials in use and regenerate natural systems.

Circularity is a strategy for reaching sustainability: it helps reducing pressure on the environment, improves the security of the supply of raw materials, boosts innovation and economic growth, produces more durable goods, creates new jobs, push to sharing economy, and deals with main global changes.

Measuring circularity is important to support informed decision making between processes, products or companies, therefore allowing for improvement of the CE. Thus, it is necessary to develop a measurement to promote its enhancement. As nowadays there is no generally accepted methodology for this, it is currently under development the international standard ISO/TC 323 on Circular Economy, where it is expected that criteria are to be defined. In the meantime, there are plenty of tools that assess circularity qualitatively or quantitatively, and a lot of foundations, studies or companies that are willing to define indicators to measure and assess CE. According to the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) report, there are four main objectives in measuring the state of art, progress and impacts of CE: raise awareness, trigger actions, make the case for circular economy, monitor performance and evaluate results (OECD, 2021).

In the context of B-WaterSmart, a water-smart society aims at boosting circularity around water and the related resources (energy, waste, etc.) according to the definition: “*societies are water-smart when they generate societal well-being via sustainable management of water resources. In water-smart societies, well-informed citizens and actors across sectors engage in continuous co-learning and innovation to develop an efficient, effective equitable and safe **circular use of water and the related resources**. This is achieved by adopting a long-term perspective to ensure water for all relevant uses, to safeguard ecosystems and their services to society, to boost value creation around water, while anticipating change towards resilient infrastructure*” (Deliverable 6.1. What is water-smartness and how to assess it?).

1.2 The importance of circular economy indicators

The European Commission launched in January 2018 a Circular Economy Monitoring Framework with the objective of helping Member States to develop a strategy, and to eventually report the general progress of the transition to a CE in the EU. By means of the implementation of a CE approach, cities have started to need indicators for monitoring their improvements and achievements. However, the lack of these indicators has been identified as a bottleneck for cities in implementing a CE strategy. Measuring the performance of cities helps them to self-assess their accomplishments, to identify barriers as well as opportunities, and to improve their actions towards a CE (Urban Agenda, 2019).

CE indicators permit to monitor the transition towards a circular economy and to measure its effects. To establish an indicator it is important to understand and define well what is to be measured, the reasons for doing it, and the target audience. In this study the indicators are understood in the context of monitoring an impact evolution and they are measures that can help to quantify how close the action

program is to desired outcomes and path. Although there may be some indicators in common among the presented monitoring frameworks, there is a clear lack of a detailed and consensual methodology to monitor the evaluation and impact of CE. For example, some indicators may be described in the same way but they are rated by different units or methods.

In order to assess the CE progress, indicators are needed in various implementation scales. According to the OECD, an indicator is a “quantitative or qualitative factor or variable that provides a simple, and reliable, means to measure achievement, to reflect the changes connected to an intervention, or to help assess the performance of a development actor” (OECD, 2013).

In the context of B-WaterSmart, indicators are considered as parameters or functions and are used to quantitatively or qualitatively assess criteria (Deliverable 6.1). Indicators considered as variables may not allow comparison among different systems.

Thus, CE indicators are the key to measure and improve circularity and from our point of view, each indicator has to be **relevant** for decision making process and stakeholders; **clearly defined** with a concise meaning; **specific** to establish exactly what is intent to measure; **achievable** with data that can be obtained with reasonable and affordable effort; **replicable**; as **universal** as possible; **time-bounded**, considering that there is a time limit to do the measurements; **quantifiable**, whenever possible, to provide an objective measurement; **distinctive** and not redundant, not measuring something already being measured by other indicator; **as few as possible**, defining only the essential indicators for an effective performance; and **useful**, making clear the area of improvement.

2 Measuring circular economy through indicators

2.1 Review of existing circular economy indicators

Considering the variety of circular economy (CE) indicators and the lack of unification to define them, it has been done an exhaustive research of different sources to collect indicators published until now and to thoroughly understand the criteria used to classify and define them. In this chapter the review of different sources will be briefly presented.

The sources analysed are the following: the OECD Report, World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD), Datalab, the European Academies' Science Advisory Council (EASAC), EU Resources Efficiency Scoreboard (EURES), the European Statistical Office (Eurostat), Council of occupational therapists for the European countries (COTEC), Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) Compass, City Blue Print Index, Water-wise cities, Ellen MacArthur Foundation, Eco-Innovation Action Plan, Ente Nazionale per l'Energia Elettrica (ENEL), the Circularity Gap Reporting Initiative (CGRI), Forètica, CityLoops project, Cradle to cradle certificate and scientific articles. Among these sources, some present a list of indicators, others provide criteria for defining or monitoring them or both indicators and criteria. In Figure 1 a classification depending on whether they present indicators or criteria is presented.

Figure 1. Classification from different sources according to whether they present CE indicators or criteria.

Hereunder, the different sources will be explained considering the referred order. The first part presents a list of indicators referred in literature, including those that does not follow the classification requirements for a performance indicator, as those used in B-WaterSmart (Alegre et al., 2016). The second part presents criteria on how to assess or monitor the indicators.

The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development Report

The OECD have developed an **Inventory of CE Indicators** with **474 indicators** collected between 2018 and 2020, which are classified in five categories (environment; economy and business; jobs; infrastructure and technology; and governance) and thirty-three sub-categories (OECD, 2021).

World Business Council for Sustainable Development

The WBCSD is an organization focused on the sustainable development that has elaborated a universal framework to measure circularity by means of **The Circular Transition Indicators (CTI) tool**, prepared to evaluate businesses of all industries, sizes, value chain positions and geographies (WBCSD, 2021).

The CTI offers a **menu of indicators** based on three models (Figure 2):

- Close the Loop: the model calculates the company's ability to close material loops.
- Optimize the Loop: these indicators illustrate how companies perform in maximizing resource efficiency beyond ensuring material loops.
- Value the Loop: the module provides information on the value that circular business creates.

Figure 2. WBCSD models classification (WBCSD, 2021).

Datalab

The French Ministry of the Environment, Energy and Marine affairs have published a document with **10 key indicators** to measure and monitor the circularity of the French economy, organized in three main areas of action and seven pillars as it can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. CE indicators classification according to Datalab (Magnier, 2017).

The CE indicators defined in this report are the following ones (Magnier, 2017):

- Domestic Material Consumption per capita
- Use of Recycled raw materials in production processes
- Household spending on product repair and maintenance
- Employment in the CE
- Number of Industrial and territorial ecology projects
- Car-sharing
- Food waste
- Resource Productivity
- Ecolabel Holders
- Quantities of waste sent to landfill

The European Academies’ Science Advisory Council

EASAC have carried out an exhaustive research of different sets of indicators that have been published in order to gather what they consider as the most relevant to monitor for CE. They have analysed sources like Eurostat, Ellen MacArthur, and World Bank among others (EASAC, 2016).

Table 4.1 Indicator sets considered in this report

Indicator set	Advocated by	Characteristic/ data source	Number of indicators
Sustainable Development Indicators	UNEP	Major global environmental issues	10
Sustainable Development Goals	UNDP	End poverty, fight inequality and injustice, and tackle climate change	17
Corporate sustainability	Global reporting initiative (GRI)	Sustainability-relevant indicators for organisations	>100
Environmental sustainability index (ESI); environmental performance indicator (EPI)	Yale and Columbia universities	Environmental indicators	21 (ESI) 20 (EPI)
Little Green Data Book	World Bank	Environment and sustainability	50
Green Growth Indicators	OECD	Environment, resources, economic and policy responses	25–30
Economy-wide material flow accounts EW-MFA	Eurostat Wuppertal Institute	Focused on material flows	6
Circular economy indicators	Ellen MacArthur foundation (EMF)	Indicators currently available	7
Resource efficiency	EU Resource Efficiency scoreboard (EURES)	Eurostat, EEA and others	32
Raw materials	European Innovation Partnership (EIP)	Raw Materials Scoreboard European Union Raw Materials Knowledge Base (EURMKB)	24 4

Figure 4. Indicator sets considered in the EASAC report (EASAC, 2016).

The EU Resources Efficiency Scoreboard

The EURES is published online by Eurostat and it collects information from European Environment Agency, Eurostat, and other European or international sources.

The Scoreboard consists of **32 indicators** classified in three levels (EU Resource Efficiency Scoreboard, 2015):

- An overall lead indicator based on resource productivity.
- A dashboard of macro indicators on materials, land, water, and carbon.
- Specific indicators to monitor the progress in achieving the key objectives and the actions established in the roadmap.

Eurostat

The European Commission has set up a monitoring framework on CE with **10 indicators** broken down into 25 sub-indicators (Eurostat, 2021).

All the indicators are available in their database and are classified in four main categories: production and consumption, waste management, secondary raw materials and competitiveness, and innovation.

COTEC Foundation

COTEC has published the first document about the evolution and state of CE in Spain and present a set of available indicators from 6 different organisations (INE, EEA, Eurostat, etc.), and separated in 15 categories such as water; environmental protection and waste; air; green economy; waste; climate change and energy; material flows; atmospheric pollution; etc. (COTEC, 2017).

SDG Compass

The SDG Compass guides companies in taking a strategic approach towards the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) and to manage and measure their contribution to these goals. The guide presents five steps to promote and increase the contribution of companies to the SDGs. Step 1, Understanding the SDGs; Step 2, Defining priorities; Step 3, Setting goals; Step 4, Integrating; and Step 5, Reporting and communicating (SDG Compass, 2021).

City Blueprint Index

The City Blueprint, provided by Utrecht University and KWR Watercycle Research Institute, is the core of the **Urban Water Atlas for Europe** which illustrates how different water management choices affect long-term sustainability of water use in cities, and informs citizens and authorities of good practices and developments that can contribute to ensure a more efficient and sustainable use of water helping to save this valuable resource. The **City Blueprint Index** provides in one infographic **25 indicators** related to water, waste, and climate change, indicating the performance of urban water resources management in a city (Utrecht University, 2021).

The Journey to Water-Wise Cities

The International Water Association (IWA) has established **17 Principles** for Water-Wise Cities which aim to help ensuring that everyone in their cities has access to safe water and sanitation. These principles are gathered in four categories: regenerative water services, water sensitive urban design, basin connected cities, and water-wise communities (IWA, 2016).

Ellen MacArthur Foundation

Ellen MacArthur foundation aims to promote the implementation of the CE concept and, with that purpose, they have implemented two different tools to assess and measure the circularity of a company or product: the **Material Circularity Indicator** and **Circulytics** (Ellen MacArthur, 2020).

Eco-Innovation Action Plan

The European Commission distinguishes between three major groups to classify the indicators:

- **Sustainable resource management:** to examine the performance of the EU Member States when contributing to lowering resources demands, increasing the security of resources and decreasing pressures on the environment on a national or international level (macro level indicators).
- **Societal behaviour:** to reflect citizen awareness and participation in the CE.
- **Business operations:** to represent eco-innovation activities focused on the adapting CE principals to business models.

Apart from that, to contribute to the CE development, they have committed to publish a set of indicators by the end of the year 2021 (Eco-innovation Action Plan, 2021).

ENEL

ENEL is an Italian multinational manufacturer and distributor of electricity and gas which has developed a circularity measurement model with five pillars of CE composed by several sub-indicators. This model considers a single circularity index that aims to evaluate the success and effectiveness of the CE and it is calculated based on two main elements: flow circularity, which considers materials and energy inputs and outputs and usage circularity, based on material usage (CirculAbility Model, 2021).

Circularity Gap Reporting Initiative

The Global Circularity Gap Report is an annual report measuring the state of circularity. It does not present indicators or criteria but metrics to measure the circular economy, tracking the progress over time. The two key metrics are the **Global Circularity Metric (GCM)** and **National Circularity Metric (NCM)** (Circular Gap Reporting initiative, 2020).

Forética

Forética represents the WBCSD in Spain and leads the Spanish Business Council for Sustainable Development composed by Presidents and CEOs of the main Spanish companies and has also driven the **Grupo de Acción en Economía Circular**, a business initiative which aims to lead the CE model (Forética, 2019).

CityLoops project

The CityLoops project aims to carry out a series of pilot actions in seven coastal European cities (Apeldoorn, Bodø, Mikkeli, Porto, Seville, Høje-Taastrup and Roskilde) to close the loop on two of the most important waste streams in Europe: construction and demolition waste, and biowaste. The major objective of the initiative is to become a circular city without resources going to waste and going towards the transition to the CE. In this sense, this project is developing a comprehensive set of indicators for circular cities including guidance on how to measure them which will be published soon in their website (Cityloops, 2020).

Cradle to Cradle Products Innovation Institute

This Institute is dedicated to driving innovation for the CE through products that have a positive impact on people and planet, and the **Cradle to Cradle Certified** is a globally recognized measure which offers business a comprehensive standard solution for going forward from commitment to action by developing safer and more sustainable products (Cradle to Cradle Products Innovation Institute, 2021).

Scientific articles

Lately, there have been published many articles about CE focused on collecting existing indicators, proposing new ones, adapting them from other sources to a specific context, suggesting criteria to establish these indicators, or in general, talking about the importance and the benefits of changing the current economic model towards a circular model that considers the minimum waste and takes advantage of every available resource in a city or region. Table 1 presents all the scientific articles that have been analysed.

Table 1. List of the scientific articles reviewed related to CE indicators analysis.

Title	Type of article/analysis	Reference
Research on Evaluation of Circular Economy Development. Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Innovation & Management.	Indicators list; Index development	Guogang and Jing, 2011
A systematic review for measuring circular economy: The 61 indicators.	Indicators list	De Pascale, et al., 2021
Advancing circular economy performance indicators and their application in Spanish companies.	Indicators adaptation	Rincón-Moreno, et al., 2020
Insights into circular economy indicators: Emphasizing dimensions of sustainability.	Bibliometric analysis; Indicators list	Martinho, 2021
An integrated approach of PCA and PROMETHEE in spatial assessment of circular economy indicators.	Comparative analysis	Stankovic, et al., 2021
Assessing the sustainability of urban eco-systems through Emergy-based circular economy indicators.	Indicators list	Santagata, et al., 2020
Exploring indicators of circular economy adoption framework through a hybrid decision support approach.	Indicators list	Yadav, et al., 2020
Circular economy indicators: What do they measure?	Classification framework	Moraga, et al., 2019
A taxonomy of circular economy indicators.	Criteria	Saidani, et al., 2019
Approaches for the evaluation of future-oriented technologies and concepts in the field of water reuse and desalination.	Study Case	Wencki, et al., 2020
Application of a decision support tool for industrial and agricultural water reuse solutions in international case studies.	Indicators list	Wencki, et al., 2020

Prioritization of sustainability indicators for promoting the circular economy: The case of developing countries.	Indicators list	Ngan, et al., 2019
Longevity and Circularity as Indicators of Eco-Efficient Resource Use in the Circular Economy.	Criteria	Figge, et al., 2018
Circular economy in cities: Reviewing how environmental research aligns with local practices.	Review	Petit-Boix and Leipold, 2018
Circular Economy: Overview of Barriers.	Bibliometric analysis	Galvão et al., 2018

From the review, it was observed that an official and homogenised framework of CE related indicators is missing. Moreover, a special focus on water and the related resources has not yet been provided. Consequently, there is a need to establish an official framework of CE related indicators related to the water sector.

2.2 Circular economy indicators approaching the water–energy–resources–waste nexus in Living Labs, cities, and regions

Nowadays, there is an increasing tendency and necessity in societies (cities, regions, etc.) to follow sustainability and circular economy policies to preserve natural resources, to boost value creation, to ensure relevant resources for all and to engage continuous co-learning and innovation. When approaching the water–energy–resources–waste nexus, circular economy (CE) indicators will allow to evaluate and monitor actions to overcome water challenges and to ensure water access and quality for the generations to come. As referred in section 2.1 from the review, an official and homogenised framework of CE related indicators is missing, particularly with this focus. Therefore, we had the necessity to adapt, combine and homogenise the existing indicators and to convert them approaching the water-energy-resources-waste nexus.

As a consequence, we developed a list of CE indicators related to the water sector and water-energy-resources-waste management through the implementation of CE principles that could meet the objectives of each LL, region, city, etc. in the context of B-WaterSmart. The proposed category classification for the indicators is presented in Table 2. The indicators are classified in **fourteen categories** and sixty-nine subcategories. The complete list of indicators can be found in the **Supplementary information** section from the present Deliverable (D4.2). The categories and subcategories adopted in this extended list come from the literature review and tried to encompass all the different sectors related to CE. For this reason, there may be some overlaps as some categories are more transversal and others are sector specific.

Table 2. List of categories and subcategories used to classify the indicators proposed.

Category	Subcategory	Category	Subcategory	
Economy and business	Added value	Eco-design	Use of secondary materials	
	Business		Use of reused parts	
	Economic efficiency		Product durability	
	Gains and revenues		Reusability	
	Investments		Recyclability	
	Productivity		End-of-life recycling input	
	Savings		Circular material use	
Water	Water consumption		Production	Circularity measures associated with production
	Water production	Material use		
	Water reclaimed	Production material reuse		
	Water efficiency	Production recycle		
	Water avoided	Production raw material avoided		
	Water emissions			
	Water cycle sustainability			
Air	Air emissions	Food	Food valorisation	
Waste	Waste generation	Society	Human health	
	Waste separation		Social impact	
	Waste recycling		Education/training	
	Waste recovering		Awareness -raising	
	Waste reduction	Governance	Collaboration	
	Waste valorisation		Financing	
	Waste treatment		Public procurement	
	Waste avoided		Regulation	
	Waste reuse		Stakeholder engagement	
Energy	Energy consumption	Competitiveness and innovation	Innovation	
	Energy from renewable sources		Patents	
	Energy reuse		Strategy and initiatives	
	Energy avoided	Monitoring and evaluation	Infrastructure and technology	Area
	Energy efficiency	Equipment		
	Energy production	Products and services		
	Bioenergy production	Construction		
Environment	Environmental safety	Green Jobs	Demolition	
	Environmental impact		Jobs and human resources	
	Environmental quality		Circular categories	

There are many ways to classify the indicators but, according to the sources that have been analysed, apart from the category and subcategory classification, each indicator is classified according to the **level** of measurement (macro, meso, micro and nano), the **methodological method** used (quantitative, semi-quantitative, and qualitative), the type of **source** analysed (companies, scientific articles and grey literature) and the **loop** definition (maintain, remain or reuse and recycle).

Figure 5. Indicators specific classification.

The level of measurement (scale) can be adapted to the necessity of each evaluable action. The European CE Monitoring Framework shows that the most **macro scale indicators** focus on preservation of materials, through strategies like recycling. However, **micro scale indicators** from literature tend to focus on other strategies considering Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) approach. According to Moraga, et al. (2019), monitoring macro scale indicators currently includes methods using energy analysis, Material Flow Analysis (MFA), and Input-Output analysis.

3 Circular economy indicators in the context of B-WaterSmart

3.1 List of circular economy indicators

Circular economy (CE) indicators are essential to measure and improve circularity. In this sense, we developed our own list of indicators to make the implementation of circularity in each LL possible. After the research on other sources, we concluded that to be efficient in guiding cities towards the improvement of circularity, CE indicators must be relevant, clearly defined, specific, achievable, replicable, universal, time-bounded, distinctive, and useful.

In the case of B-WaterSmart, a **workshop** with all the members involved in the WP4 was organized last 15th June to discuss and gather information on the main interests of each LL on the reviewed list of CE indicators. During the workshop, the importance of measuring circularity and CE indicators was explained and some ideas about how to measure these indicators were given. For the LLs the most important criterion to choose a CE indicator is that it should be relevant, achievable, and useful. Furthermore, it was mentioned in the workshop that the indicator must be scale relevant (e.g. municipal level, organization level, etc.) and applicable to the context of the LL in question. The categories most voted by the different LLs were water, environment, energy, infrastructure and technology. The less voted were eco-design, green jobs, production, and air. Other categories that were suggested were sustainability and valorisation/reuse of external waste.

The table in the **Supplementary information** (at the end of this Deliverable) shows the preferences gathered from each LL regarding the indicators for which they can collect data and which they would be interested in monitoring within the context of B-WaterSmart.

After the workshop with all the members involved in the WP4, a prioritization and simplification of the indicators as proposed initially was made. Later, the CE indicators were discussed with WP6, where a holistic water-smartness assessment framework will be developed using performance indicators. The objective was also to contribute with CE indicators to WP6, aligned with the definition of water-smartness (Deliverable 6.1) and their strategic objectives and assessment criteria. A second round showing the indicators to all interested members was done, to get the approval from the WP4 team and to get a final list of CE indicators to be monitored.

This list of **28 indicators** is shown below in Table 3, and it will be a dynamic list as it will evolve with the monitoring of the circularity of each LL and their needs. Each indicator will be adapted to a measurement scale such as macro, micro or nano, so that it can be monitored and replicated in future Water Smart Cities or regions. The scale will be established in the following deliverables. This list has also contributed to the B-WaterSmart assessment framework and more information about its contribution can be found in the **Supplementary information** section.

Table 3. Final list of circular economy indicators in the water-resources-energy-waste nexus.

Category	Indicator	Unit	Description
Economy and business	1 Potential circular economy business models	%	New and modified business models related to circular economy in the water-energy-waste nexus identified related to the existing models.
	2 Circular economy business models in practice	%	New and modified business models related to circular economy in the water-energy-waste nexus that have already been put into practice related to the existing models.
	3 Revenues of by-products	%	Potential revenues around water due to water reuse (avoided consumption, water selling) and from by-products recovered from wastewater treatment (salt, fertilizer, etc.) related to total revenues in the scope of the Living Lab (utility, industry(ies), etc.).
Water	4 Wastewater treatment efficiency index	%	Wastewater generated in the region that is treated in wastewater treatment facilities.
	5 Reclaimed water use	%	Reclaimed water used over total water consumption in the Living Lab scope (industry(ies), municipality, city or region).
	6 Potential reclaimed water use	%	Total potential of reclaimed water use over total water demand by the Living Lab scope (industry(ies), municipality, city or region). Potential of reclaimed water use definition: water demand that could be provided with reclaimed water.
	7 Reclaimed water production efficiency	%	Reclaimed water produced and used over total wastewater treated in the assessed Living Lab scope (industry(ies), municipality, city or region).
	8 Reduction of drinking water consumption	%	Water consumption for potable and non-potable use (e.g. use of non-potable groundwater for irrigation and street cleaning, use of reclaimed water for potable use) related to total water consumption.
	9 Reclaimed water distribution losses	m ⁻³ km ⁻¹	Reclaimed water loss per kilometer of reclaimed water distribution system towards its final use (e.g. irrigation, cleaning, urban use). Also applicable in the case of water supply from other non-conventional sources (e.g. rainwater distribution).
	10 Water retention from sustainable drainage systems	mm	Water supply from other non-conventional sources that is retained in an area per year, avoiding its loss. e.g. sustainable urban drainage systems (SUDs), stormwater collected for irrigation, water retention for groundwater replenishment, etc. Expressed as volume of water retained in a specific area (1 mm = 1 L m ⁻²). The area will be established according to the Living Lab scope (industry(ies), municipality, city or region).

Water	11 Water scarcity (WS)	m ³ eq m ⁻³ treated water	Quantification of the consumptive water use. Relative Available WATER REmaining per area in a watershed, after the demand of humans and aquatic ecosystems has been met. Methodology: ISO 14.046:2014. Calculation method: AWARE from WULCA (Boulay et al. 2017).
	12 Aquatic acidification (AA)	kg SO ₂ eq m ⁻³ treated water	Impact on acidity variation of the environment (water) due to the deposition of acids resulting from the release of nitrogen oxides and sulphur in the atmosphere, in the soil and in the water, which will affect the flora and fauna that inhabit it. Methodology: ISO 14.046:2014. Calculation method: Impact 2002+.
	13 Ecotoxicity (E)	CTUh eq m ⁻³ treated water	Impact on aquatic ecosystems due to toxic substances in the environment. Methodology: ISO 14.046:2014. Calculation method: USEtox2 (CTUh = comparative toxic unit for human).
	14 Eutrophication (Eu)	kg P eq m ⁻³ treated water	Impact on aquatic ecosystems due to high levels of macronutrients, nitrogen and phosphorus. Methodology: ISO 14.046:2014. Calculation method: ReCiPe (H).
	15 Water Footprint	m ³ eq m ⁻³ treated water	Single stand-alone weighted indicator. Summary from the following normalized indicators: WS, AA, E, Eu, Damage to Human Health. Calculation method: Ridoutt and Pfister 2013. In case that is not feasible to calculate it, a proxy will be used from indicators 11 to 15 and 27 (i.e. WS, AA, E, Eu, Damage to Human Health).
Air	16 Carbon Footprint (CFP)	kg CO ₂ eq m ⁻³ treated water	Calculated from Global warming potential 100 years (GWP) - IPCC indicator for calculating the carbon footprint.
	17 Climate Change mitigation index	%	Emissions avoided as a consequence of recovery and reuse of subproducts. Calculated from an increase/decrease: (kg CO ₂ eq m ⁻³ treated water year 1 - kg CO ₂ eq m ⁻³ treated water year 0)/kg CO ₂ eq m ⁻³ treated water year 0.
	18 Greenhouse gas emissions reduction	t CO ₂ eq m ⁻³ treated water	Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions reduction due to efficiency of energy consumption and renewable energy.
Waste	19 Water-related materials' recovery	%	Recovered waste over total waste (of the same type) entering the wastewater treatment plant/Living Lab scope (industry(ies), municipality, city or region). It can be done for nutrients such as phosphorus (P) and nitrogen (N), sodium chloride (NaCl), etc. e.g. P recovered over total g P entering the wastewater treatment plant. If more than one waste flow is recovered, a weighting factor will be applied to obtain a unique total indicator.

Waste	20 Fertilizer production avoided	%	Nitrogen (N)/phosphorus (P) recovered by fertirrigation over the N/P used (fertirrigation and added) in the Living Lab scope (industry(ies), municipality, city or region). From this indicator it can be obtained: avoided production costs, avoided production, avoided emissions for the production of commercial fertilizers (only a part of the total commercial fertilizer needed).
	21 Sludge beneficial use	%	Sludge with beneficial use (land application for agronomic purposes, composting, energy production) over total sludge produced.
Energy	22 Energy consumption ratio	kWh m ⁻³	Net average energy consumption for abstraction/treatment of water/wastewater per cubic meter of water produced/treated.
	23 Renewable energy consumption ratio	%	Renewable energy consumption for abstraction/treatment of water/wastewater over total energy consumption.
	24 Energy production from waste recovered	kWh kg waste ⁻¹	Energy produced from waste recovered (e.g. anaerobic digestion, sludge, ice cream, food waste, etc.).
	25 Green reclaimed water efficiency	kWh m ⁻³	Renewable energy consumption per cubic meter of reclaimed water produced.
Environment	26 Ecosystem environmental benefits generation	%	Calculated from an increase/decrease of "Damage to Ecosystems / Water Deprivation Effect to Ecosystems": - (Damage year 1 - Damage year 0)/Damage year 0. (Damage to Ecosystems units: PDF m ² year m ⁻³ treated water). The Damage to Ecosystems (or Water Deprivation Effect to Ecosystems) represents the loss of species in an ecosystem by consuming water. Methodology: ISO 14.046:2014. Calculation method: AWARE.
Society	27 Human health benefits generation	%	Calculated from an increase/decrease of "Damage to Human Health / Human toxicity": -(Damage year 1 - Damage year 0)/Damage year 0. (Damage to Human Health units: DALY m ⁻³ treated water). The Damage to Human Health (or Toxicity to Human) represents the impact of mortality and disability associated with specific diseases, in different communities. Methodology: ISO 14.046:2014. Calculation method: USEtox2.
Green Jobs	28 Employment in the circular economy	%	Number of green jobs created in the circular economy context in comparison with total jobs created.

These indicators will be calculated from the data gathered from different LLs and their regions, cities, etc. according to the specifications from Task 4.1 and Deliverable 4.1 "Manual of data specifications required for mapping of actors at Living Labs".

The main objective of the results of this D4.2 and the calculation of the indicators will be the assessment, identification and monitoring of the different circular opportunities identified during the development of Task 4.2 until the end of the project. Those circular opportunities will also be connected and coordinated with the CoPs architecture and stakeholder mapping for each LL from WP1 (Deliverable 1.1).

From now and until the end of the project, data will start to be gathered from the LLs periodically to start the identification and monitoring of the circular opportunities and finally get an overview of performance regarding circularity during the next years. The frequency of evaluation of each indicator will depend on the scope of the LL (industry(ies), municipality, city, region, etc.) and will be adapted for each case also depending on the data availability. It is expected to evaluate the indicators yearly, as a minimum frequency, to get a valuable circularity performance assessment until the end of the project, but also this monitoring could be extended beyond.

3.2 Circular economy indicators according to new emergent guidelines and standards

To move towards a CE and to achieve the targets to reduce the climate emergency we are facing, it is necessary to increase the collaboration among policymakers, economic sectors and society. To achieve this, some emerging strategies and guidelines are being developed such as ISO/TC 323 on Circular Economy and the EU Taxonomy - Circular economy environmental objective.

The **ISO/TC 323** objective is to develop frameworks, guidance, supporting tools and requirements for the implementation of activities of the involved organisations, to maximise the contribution to sustainable development. This is still under development by a technical committee of different experts in this field.

Figure 6. Environmental objectives fixed by the EU Taxonomy. Source: EU Technical Expert Group on Sustainable Finance.

The **EU Taxonomy** is a classification system for sustainable economic activities. It will provide advice to stakeholders, investors, companies, and policymakers about which economic activities can be considered more environmentally sustainable. The main goal is to allocate and prioritize investments to those sustainable projects and to help business to go towards a more circular and climate-friendly economy. Furthermore, this would help to accomplish the European Commission climate and energy targets for 2030 and to enhance the achievement of the European Green Deal objectives for 2050.

The EU Taxonomy establishes six environmental objectives shown in Figure 6.

Currently, the first two objectives (climate change mitigation and climate change adaptation) are almost to be legally binding by January 2022. For the remaining objectives, a preliminary technical criterion will be adopted by the end of this year and is expected to be legally binding by 2023. More specifically, the fourth objective “Transition to a circular economy” will serve as a guideline to follow for each activity in each LL.

Furthermore, from the two first climate change objectives, a technical criterion has been published and some of these criteria have been already adapted preliminarily for the B-WaterSmart CE list of indicators (Table 4).

Table 4. EU Taxonomy contribution criteria already adapted to the B-WaterSmart CE list of indicators.

Category	Description	Unit	Taxonomy contribution criteria	Indicator for B-WaterSmart
Water	Annual percentage of rainwater that is retained in a defined area	%	"One of the following impact indicators will be declared and calculated in the design of Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems: 1. The percentage of a defined area, e.g. a residential or commercial area, where rain water is not directly drained but retained within the area site. 2. The estimated annual percentage of rainwater that is retained in a defined area."	10 Water retention from sustainable drainage systems
	Phosphorus recovery from wastewater	%	"For the processes integrated at the WWTP (mainly Struvite– magnesium ammonium phosphate, $H_4MgPO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$), P recovery processes will recover at least 10% of the incoming P load."	19 Water-related materials' recovery
Energy	Net energy consumption of a wastewater treatment plant	kWh p.e. ⁻¹ (kilowatt hour/ population equivalent)	"The net energy consumption of the wastewater treatment plant equals to or is lower than: 1. 35 kWh per population equivalent (p.e.) per annum for treatment plant capacity below 10,000 p.e.; 2. 25 kWh per population equivalent (p.e.) per annum for treatment plant capacity between 10,000 and 100,000 p.e.; 3. 20 kWh per population equivalent (p.e.) per annum for treatment plant capacity above 100,000 p.e."	22 Energy consumption ratio
	Energy consumption per water produced	kWh m ⁻³ produced water	"The net average energy consumption for abstraction and treatment equals to or is lower than 0.5 kWh per cubic meter produced water supply."	

The ISO/TC 323 and the EU Taxonomy will be used as strategic approaches in the context of B-WaterSmart. As they are still under development, the future deliverables and hence, the list of indicators, may suffer some changes in order to be adapted to this new context.

4 Conclusions

To sum up, the current linear economic model is no longer sustainable, and it requires a big change in the way societies produce and consume. For this reason, it is important to move towards a circular economy (CE) model where waste is minimised, and every resource is harnessed. Therefore, it is essential to assess circularity based on a set of CE indicators to measure and improve circularity as well as to drive towards a more sustainable culture.

Nowadays, there are many publications from companies, organisations, scientific articles, etc., presenting lists of indicators or criteria to define its sustainability contribution, but there is still a clear lack of unification and a consensual methodology to monitor the evaluation and impact of the CE. To solve this, the availability of a standardised and homogenised framework would be a great step to enhance circularity and sustainability. For this reason, it is expected that guidelines and standards currently under development such as ISO/TC 323 and EU Taxonomy will define the way forward in the forthcoming years.

This deliverable (D4.2) presents a list of different sources and scientific articles reviewed and updated until today about CE related indicators. It also presents a proposal list of 28 CE indicators related to the water sector and the water-energy-resources-waste nexus. This set of indicators provides a contribution to be considered in the development of the water-smartness assessment framework of B-WaterSmart. These indicators will allow to measure and assess circularity and identify circular opportunities in six coastal cities and regions, named LLs, to get an overview of its performance until the end of the project and beyond. Results from the evaluation of the different indicators will allow to analyse the performance of the LLs and to implement different strategies to enhance its sustainability.

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Supplementary information

Reviewed list of CE indicators

Table 5. Preliminary and reviewed list of CE indicators considering all the literature review and Living Labs preferences.

<p>Considerations taken in this table:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FU: Functional Unit. Unit of interest for each region, which can be applied as m³ of treated waste, population equivalent, etc. • Int. Cmte. about CE: International Committee about Circular Economy • Ad.: Adapted • LL1 AI: Living Lab 1 Alicante • LL2 Li: Living Lab 2 Lisbon • LL3 Ve: Living Lab 3 Venice • LL4 FI: Living Lab 4 Flanders • LL5 EF: Living Lab 5 East Frisia • LL6 Bo: Living Lab 6 Bodo <p>The LL2 Lisbon made a global analysis on the list of CE indicators, instead of presenting suggestion for each indicator. The contributions and preferences were: Prioritization of the use of freshwater resources, water use efficiency, water reuse, water-related energy use, energy recovery, nutrient recovery, mineral recovery, recovery of other relevant resources. To keep aside awareness and social acceptance indicators which will be considered by Work WP5 (Society, governance, policy, social acceptance and barriers).</p>									
Category	Subcategory	Indicators and sub-indicators	Unit	SUMMARY LLs					Short reference
				LL1 AI	LL3 Ve	LL4 FI	LL5 EF	LL6 Bo	
Economy and business	Added value	Net added value of the circular economy	€		x				OECD
		Value added at factor cost	% GDP at current prices						OECD
		Added local economic value associated to circular economy actions	€ per FU	x	x				OECD
	Business	Number of companies or products with tax benefits to incentivize the circular economy	number		x				OECD
		Circular business	% total		x			x	OECD

		New revenue models related to the circular economy	number	x	x	x	x		OECD	
	Economic efficiency	Energy intensity	toe· million € ⁻¹						x	OECD
		Material intensity	kg € ⁻¹							OECD
		Generation of waste per €	kg € ⁻¹							Ad. from EUROSTAT
		Economic growth of the circular economy	% GDP							OECD
		Economic value of the resources used and the value at the time they are reintroduced into the system	NA				x			OECD
	Economic structure	GDP per Total Greenhouse Gas Emissions	PPP·kg CO ₂ eq ⁻¹						x	OECD
		Weight of the green economy in GDP	%							OECD
	Gains and revenues	Industry turnover in more circular products	thousand million €							OECD
		Opportunity cost through the circular economy process	€	x						Int. Cmte. about CE
	Investments	Funding to enhance the implementation of projects for the reuse of regenerated water from wastewater	€	x	x	x	x			OECD
		Investment in research for increasing circular knowledge and expertise	€	x		x				OECD
		Amount invested in circular economy projects	€		x			x		OECD
	Productivity	Resource/material productivity	€ kg ⁻¹							OECD
	Savings	Money saved (in comparison with purchasing new) through the reuse and recovery of materials	€	x					x	OECD
		Cost savings	€	x	x				x	OECD
		Waste reduction economic savings	€	x		x				OECD
Water	Water consumption	Water consumption per unit	million m ³	x			x	x	OECD	
		Total drinking water consumption	L pers ⁻¹ dia ⁻¹	x			x	x	COTEC	
		Water extraction, direct	million m ³	x		x	x		OECD	
		Direct water withdrawal/total water withdrawal	%	x		x	x		Conama	

		Water Exploitation Index Plus	number	x		x			Conama	
		Water Use Efficiency Index	number		x		x	x	Int. Cmte. about CE	
	Water production		Percentage of urban wastewater treated / total wastewater generated	%	x		x	x	x	OECD
			Desalinated water/total water withdrawal	%			x	x		Conama
	Water reclaimed		Regenerated water used as a source of water supply	%	x	x	x			OECD
			Reclaimed water over wastewater generated	%	x	x	x			Ad. from OECD
			Fit-for-purpose allocation	m ³ year ⁻¹						B-WaterSmart
	Water efficiency		Drinking water savings	m ³ year ⁻¹	x			x	x	OECD
			Water loss reduction	m ³ year ⁻¹ or %	x		x	x	x	B-WaterSmart
	Water avoided		Freshwater consumption reduction due to reclaimed water use	m ³ year ⁻¹ or %	x	x	x	x		B-WaterSmart
	Water emissions		Direct emissions to water	g L ⁻¹	x		x			Int. Cmte. about CE
			Eutrophication	kg P eq. or kg N eq.	x			x		Int. Cmte. about CE
	Urban water cycle sustainability		Blue City Index	%	x		x		x	KWR
Water cycle sustainability		Water Footprint	m ³ eq. m ⁻³ supplied or m ³ eq. per FU		x				Int. Cmte. about CE	
Air	Air emissions		Carbon footprint (direct + indirect GHG emissions)	t CO ₂ eq. year ⁻¹ (or per FU)	x	x		x	OECD	
			GHG emissions from sustainable transport versus conventional transport	%					x	DATALAB
			Direct GHG emissions	t CO ₂ eq. year ⁻¹ (or per FU)	x				x	OECD
	Air emissions savings/reduction		GHG avoided as a consequence of recovery and reuse of materials	t CO ₂ eq. year ⁻¹ (or per FU)	x					OECD
			GHG emissions reduction	t CO ₂ eq. year ⁻¹ (or per FU)	x				x	OECD
			GHG savings as a result of procurement activities	t CO ₂ eq. year ⁻¹ (or per FU)						OECD
Waste	Waste generation		For each waste/emissions flow X	t per FU					Int. Cmte. about CE	
			Mass of solid waste	t year ⁻¹ (or per FU)				x	OECD	

		Total amount of waste generated	t year ⁻¹ (or per FU)	x				x	OECD
		Generation of waste per material consumption	%						Ad. from EUROSTAT
		Total waste treatment: Landfill	t year ⁻¹ (or per FU)	x					OECD
	Waste separation	Waste separation ratio	%					x	OECD
	Waste recycling	Ratio of "any material" recycling to its quantity used/acquired	%						Ad. from OECD
		Fraction that is recycled	% or t per FU		x			x	Int. Cmte. about CE
		Recycling rate	% or kg cap ⁻¹ day ⁻¹	x				x	EUROSTAT
	Waste recovering	Amount of recovered material through an inclusive recycling programme	% or t per FU						OECD
		Percentage of recovered waste over generated	%		x	x			OEC
	Waste reduction	Reduction of generated waste	%						OECD
	Waste valorisation	Fraction that is reused	% or t per FU			x			Int. Cmte. about CE
		Quantity of bio-waste managed by on-site composting	% or t per FU						OECD
		Total waste treatment: Incineration	t year ⁻¹ (or per FU)	x					OECD
	Waste avoided	Waste avoided	t year ⁻¹ (or per FU)						OECD
	Waste reuse	(% reuse rate)	%		x				Int. Cmte. about CE
		Reuse of packaging waste	%						OECD
		Waste reuse via other external activities	t year ⁻¹ (or per FU)	x					OECD
Energy	Energy consumption	Total/specific flow energy input	kWh per FU			x	x	x	Int. Cmte. about CE
		Electrical energy consumption	MW or MWh year ⁻¹	x	x			x	OECD
		Fuel consumption	ktoe						OECD
		Energy consumption for transportation	kWh per FU					x	Int. Cmte. about CE
		Biofuel consumption	ktoe						OECD
	Energy from renewable sources	Renewable energy consumption	% of energy use	x				x	OECD
		Electricity production from renewable sources	GWh or MW	x				x	OECD

		The share of renewable energy in district heating	%						OECD
		Fraction of energy produced from renewable sources	%						Int. Cmte. about CE
	Energy reuse	Energy recovery through circularity implementation	kWh	x					Int. Cmte. about CE
	Energy avoided	Energy consumption avoidance from solutions from energy and water resources recovery	kWh	x		x			OECD
	Energy efficiency	Energy savings	kWh year ⁻¹	x				x	OECD
		Eco-efficiency	kg CO ₂ eq. € ⁻¹	x					Int. Cmte. about CE
	Energy/ Bioenergy production	Gross electricity production	GWh						OECD
		Installed MW of biomass generation	MW	x				x	OECD
Environment	Environmental safety	Contribution to maintain ecosystem services	value scale	x		x	x		Wencki et al. 2020
	Environmental impact	Products and construction techniques covered by life cycle analysis studies	number			x			OECD
		Life cycle assessment	many units		x	x		x	Int. Cmte. about CE
	Environmental quality	Land use, direct	% cultured land						OECD
Ecodesign	Use of secondary materials	Secondary materials consumption	t						Int. Cmte. about CE
	Use of reused parts	Reused parts consumption	t						Int. Cmte. about CE
	Product durability	Duration of a product during all the life cycle	time units						Int. Cmte. about CE
	Reusability	Quantity of components designed to be reused	%						Int. Cmte. about CE
	Recyclability	Recycling rate of "any material" packaging	%						EUROSTAT
	End-of-life recycling input	End-of-life recycling input rate	%						EUROSTAT
	Circular material use	Circular material use rate	%					x	
Contribution of recycled materials to the demand for raw materials		%							OECD

		Material circularity indicator (for a product)	%						Ellen MacArthur Fdn.
		Circular material use rate	number						EUROSTAT
Production	Circularity measures associated with production	Mass of flow	kg						Int. Cmte. about CE
		Reduction of incoming / outgoing flows	%						OECD
		Cyclical use rate	% of total						OECD
		Ratio of equipment reused/repaired to new equipment acquired	%						Int. Cmte. about CE
	Material use - inputs (non-production)	Consumption of raw materials	t per FU						OECD
		Consumption of secondary materials	t per FU						OECD
		Consumption of non-EU materials	t per FU						OECD
	Material use - lifetime	Actual average technical lifetime of a material/product	time units						Int. Cmte. about CE
	Production material reuse	Materials recovered through reuse	t or increased %						OECD
		Fraction of reuse content	%						Int. Cmte. about CE
	Production recycle	Materials recovered through recycling	t or increased %				x		OECD
		Fraction of recycled content	%						EUROSTAT
		Fraction of renewable content	%						Int. Cmte. about CE
	Production raw material avoided	Raw material avoided	t per FU or %						OECD
		Material savings	kt						OECD
Production of by-products	By-product production yield	% or t per FU		x				Int. Cmte. about CE	
Food	Food valorisation	Food waste	Mt	x					EUROSTAT
Society	Human health	Health protection from pathogenic microorganisms from water reuse	value scale	x	x	x	x		Wencki et al. 2020
	Social impact	Acceptance for any circular economy strategy applied	value scale	x	x		x	x	Wencki et al. 2020
	Education/training	Number of training courses/workshops on the circular economy	number						OECD
		Actions taken to disseminate water efficiency guides	number		x		x	x	x

		People trained in the circular economy fields of activity	number or %				x		OECD	
		Circular economy researchers	number						OECD	
	Awareness - raising		Publications on the circular and solidarity economy	number	x				x	OECD
			Number of users actively involved in a platform of good practices and relevant stakeholders	number	x	x				OECD
			Strengthening environmental awareness	value scale	x	x	x		x	Wencki et al. 2020
			Awareness actions/events/campaigns on search and innovation on the circular economy and their respective impact	number	x		x	x		OECD
			Number of participating people on awareness raising activities	number	x		x			OECD
			Awareness on the efficient water use	number	x		x		x	B-WaterSmart
Governance	Collaboration	Financial institutions willing to collaborate on a circular economy initiative	%						OECD	
		Number of synergies identified / implemented by economic actors	number	x			x		OECD	
		Agreements for acceptance of by-products and materials with end-of-waste status	number	x			x		Ad. from OECD	
		Number of meetings of a working group to boost sharing	number	x		x			OECD	
	Financing	Financial assistance granted to companies related to the circular economy and new circular business models	€					x		OECD
		Total budget allocated to circular economy development	€	x		x				España Circular 2030
		Budget amount assigned to calls for projects/living labs carried out/implemented and number of companies that have benefited from them	€							OECD
	Public procurement	Good practices on public procurement identified and disseminated	number	x	x				x	OECD
		Public procurement contracts with a circular economy dimension	%	x		x			x	OECD

		Public procurement contracts with an environmental clause and/or criteria	%	x				x	OECD
		Green public procurement	%	x				x	EUROSTAT
		Identified legal barriers for the Green Public Procurement	number						OECD
	Regulation	Directives adopted to improve water efficiency and water reuse	number	x	x	x	x		OECD
		Number of circular policy advisers developing circular regulations and change 'linear' regulations	number				x		OECD
		Legal and regulatory barriers to the circular economy removed (identified and resolved)	number			x			OECD
		New laws and regulations that discourage linear practices (e.g. resource tax, public circular procurement, resource passport)	number						OECD
	Stakeholder engagement	Number of events held in collaboration with the social entrepreneurship community	number						OECD
		Number of economic actors mobilised in different actions/initiatives for the circular economy	number	x		x	x		OECD
		Network meetings for circular projects	number	x		x		x	OECD
Competitiveness and innovation	Innovation, pilots, and experiments	Implementation of an innovation platform for the circular economy	YES/NO	x	x				OECD
		Number of start-ups supported by an innovation platform	number					x	OECD
		Number of experimental/research projects initiated with a circular economy strategy	number			x	x		OECD
		Total number of developed circular economy projects	number	x		x	x	x	DATALAB
		Initiatives on reuse, recovery or recycling materials	number	x	x	x			Ad. from OECD
		Technology transfer actions on the circular economy (from innovation to implementation)	number or value scale						B-WaterSmart
	Patents	Patents (technology, product design)	number						OECD
		Number of patents related to circular economy, recycling and secondary raw materials	number						EUROSTAT

	Strategy and initiatives	Market position, competition	value scale				x		Wencki et al. 2020	
		Creation of a municipal or regional web platform for information on the the circular economy	YES/NO					x	OECD	
		Number of projects implemented for the valorisation of energy and recovered water resources	number	x				x	OECD	
		Increase in initiatives for a green and circular economy, in terms of renewable energies, sustainable mobility and energy efficiency	number					x	OECD	
		Total number of approved water reuse projects	number·year ⁻¹			x	x		OECD	
	Monitoring and evaluation	Sustainability reports published	number	x				x	Ad. from OECD	
		Maps of local resources	number					x	x	OECD
		Follow-up and monitoring of the results of circular economy actions/projects	value scale							OECD
	Infrastructure and technology	Area	Space requirement	m ² or m ² m ⁻³				x		Wencki et al. 2020
Land/area incorporating the principles of the circular economy			ha or ha year ⁻¹				x		OECD	
Number of positive externalities from the installed spaces for the sharing economy and donation			value scale							OECD
Equipment		Tolerance of disturbance against external perturbations	value scale				x		Wencki et al. 2020	
Products and services		New circular products	number	x	x		x		OECD	
Construction		Construction works with circular design	%	x				x		OECD
		Avoided use of raw materials for construction	%	x				x		Int. Cmte. about CE
		Rate of compliance with the obligation to use at least 5% of recycled materials in construction contracts	rate	x						OECD
		Construction waste	t per FU	x				x	x	OECD
		Construction waste usage/recovery rate	%	x						EUROSTAT
	Recovery rate of construction waste	%	x					x	OECD	

		Recycling rate of construction waste	%	x				x	EUROSTAT
	Demolition	Demolition waste	t per FU					x	OECD
		Demolition waste usage/recovery rate	%					x	OECD
		Recovery rate of demolition waste	%					x	OECD
		End-of-Life (EoL)	value scale						Int. Cmte. about CE
Green Jobs	Jobs and human resources	PhD and post-PhD grants and contracts in scientific employment	number						OECD
		Jobseekers who have been employed as a result of training developed under a circular economy program	number						Ad. from OECD
		Employment in the Circular Economy	number or %	x	x		x		EUROSTAT
		Number of green jobs created and secured	number						OECD
	People actively working on the development of a circular vision	number	x				x	OECD	
Circular categories	Ecolabel Holders / number of ecolabels assigned	number						Int. Cmte. about CE	

Contribution of CE indicators from WP4 to the B-WaterSmart assessment framework

Table 6. Contribution of circular economy indicators from WP4 to the B-WaterSmart assessment framework.

Vision: Water Smart Society											
#	Societies are water-smart when they generate societal well-being via sustainable management of water resources. In water-smart societies, well-informed citizens and actors across sectors engage in continuous co-learning and innovation (SO E) to develop an efficient, effective, equitable and safe circular use of water and the related resources. This is achieved by adopting a long-term perspective to ensure water for all relevant uses (SO A), to safeguard ecosystems and their services to society (SO B), to boost value creation around water (SO C), while anticipating change towards resilient infrastructure (SO D).										
B-WaterSmart Assessment framework											
The B-WaterSmart framework supports the creation and implementation of strategic plans to achieve the water-smart society vision							WP4 team				
Framework structure											
No.	Strategic Objective (SO)	Soc	Env	Econ	Tech	Gov	Assessment criteria (AC)	Metric short title	Metric description - free text	Indicator	Unit
#.1	A. Ensuring water for all relevant uses	++	+	+	+	+	A.1 Safe and secure fit-for-purpose water provision	-	-	-	-
							A.2 Accessibility and equity (for people and for other uses)	-	-	-	-
							A.3 Financial viability	-	-	-	-
#.2	B. Safeguarding ecosystems and their services to society		++				B.1 Safeguarded water ecosystems	Ecosystem benefits	Ecosystem environmental benefits generation	Calculated from an increase/decrease of "Damage to Ecosystems": -(Damage year 1 - Damage year 0)/Damage year 0. (Damage to Ecosystems units: DALY m-3 treated water). The Damage to Ecosystems represents the loss of species in an ecosystem by consuming water.	%
							B.2 Enhanced ecosystem services to society	Society benefits	Human health benefits generation	Calculated from an increase/decrease of "Damage to Human Health / Human toxicity": -(Damage year 1 - Damage year 0)/Damage year 0. (Damage to Human Health units: DALY m-3 treated water). The Damage to Human Health represents the impact of mortality and disability associated with specific diseases, in different communities.	%

#.2	B. Safeguarding ecosystems and their services to society		++	+	B.3 Resource efficiency	Wastewater treatment	Wastewater treatment efficiency index	Wastewater generated in the region that is treated in wastewater treatment facilities.	%
						Reclaimed water	Potential reclaimed water use	Total potential of reclaimed water use over total water demand by the Living Lab scope (industry(ies), municipality, city or region). Potential of reclaimed water use definition: water demand that could be provided with reclaimed water.	%
						Reclaimed water	Reclaimed water production efficiency	Reclaimed water produced and used over total wastewater treated in the assessed Living Lab scope (industry(ies), municipality, city or region).	%
						Reclaimed water	Reclaimed water distribution losses	Reclaimed water loss per kilometer of reclaimed water distribution system towards its final use (e.g. irrigation, cleaning, urban use). Also applicable in the case of water supply from other non-conventional sources (e.g. rainwater distribution).	m ⁻³ km ⁻¹
						Water Footprint	Water Footprint	Single stand-alone weighted indicator. Summary from the following normalized indicators: Water Scarcity (WS), Aquatic Acidification (AA), Ecotoxicity (E), Eutrophication (Eu) and Human Toxicity (HT). Calculation method: Ridoutt and Pfister 2013. In case that is not feasible to calculate it, a proxy will be used from separated indicators (i.e. WS, AA, E, Eu, HT).	m ³ eq m ⁻³ treated water
						Carbon Footprint	Carbon Footprint	Calculated from Global warming potential 100 years (GWP) - IPCC indicator for calculating the carbon footprint.	kg CO ₂ eq m ⁻³ treated water
						Carbon neutrality	Climate change mitigation index	Emissions avoided as a consequence of recovery and reuse of subproducts. Calculated from an increase/decrease: (kg CO ₂ eq m ⁻³ treated water year 1 - kg CO ₂ eq m ⁻³ treated water year 0)/kg CO ₂ eq m ⁻³ treated water year 0.	%
						Energy efficiency	Greenhouse gas emissions reduction	Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions reduction due to efficiency of energy consumption and renewable energy.	t CO ₂ eq m ⁻³ treated water
						Energy consumption	Energy consumption ratio	Net average energy consumption for abstraction/treatment of water/wastewater per cubic meter of water produced/treated.	kWh m ⁻³
						Energy consumption	Renewable energy consumption ratio	Renewable energy consumption for abstraction/treatment of water/wastewater over total energy consumption.	%
Green efficiency	Green reclaimed water efficiency	Renewable energy consumption per cubic meter of reclaimed water produced.	kWh m ⁻³						

#.2	B. Safeguarding ecosystems and their services to society		++	+		B.4 Resilience to climate change	Reclaimed water	Reclaimed water use	Reclaimed water used over total water consumption in the Living Lab scope (industry(ies), municipality, city or region).	%
							Water consumption	Reduction of drinking water consumption	Water consumption for potable and non-potable use (e.g. use of non-potable groundwater for irrigation and street cleaning, use of reclaimed water for potable use) related to total water consumption.	%
							Water retention	Water retention from sustainable drainage systems	Water supply from other non-conventional sources that is retained in an area per year, avoiding its loss. e.g. sustainable urban drainage systems (SUDs), stormwater collected for irrigation, water retention for groundwater replenishment, etc. Expressed as volume of water retained in a specific area (1 mm = 1 L m ⁻²). The area will be established according to the Living Lab scope (industry(ies), municipality, city or region).	mm
#.3	C. Boosting value creation around water					C.1 Circular policy making (new name instead of: Decision and policy making)	-	-	-	-
						C.2 New circular business models	Business models	Potential circular economy business models	New and modified business models related to circular economy in the water-energy-waste nexus identified related to the existing models.	%
							Business models	Circular economy business models in practice	New and modified business models related to circular economy in the water-energy-waste nexus that have already been put into practice related to the existing models.	%
						C.3 Resource recovery	Waste recovery	Water-related materials' recovery	Recovered waste over total waste (of the same type) entering the wastewater treatment plant/Living Lab scope (industry(ies), municipality, city or region). It can be done for nutrients such as phosphorus (P) and nitrogen (N), sodium chloride (NaCl), etc. e.g. P recovered over total g P entering the wastewater treatment plant. If more than one waste flow is recovered, a weighting factor will be applied to obtain a unique total indicator.	%
Nutrient recovery	Fertilizer production avoided	Nitrogen (N)/phosphorus (P) recovered by fertirrigation over the N/P used (fertirrigation and added) in the Living Lab scope (industry(ies), municipality, city or region). From this indicator it can be obtained: avoided production costs, avoided production, avoided emissions for the production of commercial fertilizers (only a part of the total commercial fertilizer needed).	%							

#.3	C. Boosting value creation around water			++	+	+	C.3 Resource recovery	Sludge application	Sludge beneficial use	Sludge with beneficial use (land application for agronomic purposes, composting, energy production) over total sludge produced.	%
								Energy valorisation	Energy production from waste recovered	Energy produced from waste recovered (e.g. anaerobic digestion, sludge, ice cream, food waste, etc.).	kWh kg waste ⁻¹
							C.4 Water circular economy growth	By-products generated	Revenues of by-products	Potential revenues around water due to water reuse (avoided consumption, water selling) and from by-products recovered from wastewater treatment (salt, fertilizer, etc.) related to total revenues in the scope of the Living Lab (utility, industry(ies), etc.).	%
								Green jobs	Employment in the circular economy	Number of green jobs created in the circular economy context in comparison with total jobs created.	%
							C.5 Level of ambition (new name instead of management ambition)	-	-	-	-
#.4	D. Promoting adaptive change towards resilient infrastructure				++	D.1 Long term planning for infrastructure investments towards circularity and resilience	-	-	-	-	
						D.2 Shortening of the distribution and use chains	-	-	-	-	
						D.3 Technology implementation (from pilot to large scale plant)	-	-	-	-	
						D.4 Measure of robustness (need to identify parameter) of water systems due to transformation	-	-	-	-	
#.5	E. Engaging citizens and actors across sectors in continuous co-learning and innovation	+			++	E.1 Awareness	-	-	-	-	
						E.2 Multi-level network potential	-	-	-	-	
						E.3 Stakeholder Engagement processes	-	-	-	-	
						E.4 Capacity building	-	-	-	-	
						E.5 Information and knowledge sharing (replacing: useful knowledge)	-	-	-	-	

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